

Design of a Fast Reactor Core for Shipping Applications: Key Requirements

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ABSTRACT

The integration of nuclear power systems in ships presents a complex engineering challenge, with the reactor core design at its center. The reactor core must be compact and lightweight to conform to shipboard constraints, yet capable of delivering long operational life—ideally from 10 to 20 years—under variable load conditions. It must ensure robust radiation protection, precise reactivity control, reliable cooling, and shutdown mechanisms, while operating in the dynamic marine environment. These demands necessitate innovative design approaches that diverge significantly from terrestrial reactor technologies. This paper identifies and analyzes the key requirements for a reactor core suitable for marine deployment, highlighting their interdependence and their influence on the overall reactor architecture.

Keywords: Ships' powering, Core design, Monte Carlo burnup calculation, LFR.

1. INTRODUCTION

The decarbonization of the maritime sector has become a pressing priority, requiring increasing attention from major stakeholders across the shipping industry. Maritime transport is recognized as a significant contributor to global greenhouse gas emissions [1], prompting the search for cleaner, more sustainable powering technologies.

Among the alternatives to conventional fossil marine fuels, nuclear power has emerged as a promising solution. While e-fuels, such as ammonia, methanol, and hydrogen, are under consideration, they present substantial challenges in terms of safety, production costs, market availability, and logistical complexity [2]. In contrast, nuclear energy offers high energy density, zero carbon emissions, and the potential for long-duration operation without refueling—features particularly attractive for large ocean going ships [3].

A critical aspect of implementing nuclear power on ships lies in the design of the reactor core. This task involves reconciling the compactness and weight constraints typical of marine applications with the demanding requirements of long core life, variable load-following capability, radiation protection, reactivity control, and robust safety systems. These challenges are especially pronounced in the context of advanced reactor concepts such as Lead-cooled Fast Reactors (LFRs).

This paper presents and analyzes the key design requirements for a reactor core suitable for marine deployment, with a specific focus on lead-cooled fast reactor technology. The standard and marine-derived requirements will be explained, as will a series of possible approaches to address them.

2. SIZE AND WEIGHT

The typical total power demand for large ocean going ships nuclear-powered ships ranges from approximately 30 MW to over 100 MW of equivalent electrical output, depending on the ship's size, operating profile, and cruise speed [4]. Achieving this level of power within the spatial and weight constraints of a marine platform presents a significant engineering challenge. Consequently, the reactor core, associated systems, and structural components must be designed to be compact and lightweight, without compromising either safety or performance.

The available volume and mass allocation for the reactor system vary with ship class, but in most cases, smaller reactor footprints are preferred to maximize cargo capacity and maintain ship stability. This

drives the need for high power density within the core, extracting maximum thermal output from minimal volume. However, increasing power density introduces trade-offs. Higher neutron fluxes and thermal loads accelerate material degradation, particularly in reactor vessel components exposed to intense radiation. Moreover, compact designs necessitate thicker and more extensive radiation shielding, which adds weight and complexity. These challenges are amplified in fast-spectrum reactors, such as LFR, where the absence of a moderating medium results in more energetic neutron spectrum compared to pressurized water reactors.

3. CORE LIFE-TIME

Core lifetime is a critical design constraint for marine reactors, requiring long-duration operation with minimal refueling, reactivity control, and non-proliferation limits. A crucial requirement for nuclear reactors intended for marine applications is the extended core lifetime, ideally matching the operational lifespan of the ship itself, often 20 years or more. This long-duration operation minimizes the need for refueling infrastructure, reduces operational downtime, and enhances the economic viability of nuclear power in commercial fleets [5].

To achieve such a long-life, the reactor must be designed with sufficient reactivity excess at the beginning of life. This ensures that the core remains critical throughout its fuel cycle, compensating for fuel depletion and the buildup of neutron-absorbing products. However, managing this reactivity excess requires careful control of the reactivity swing, which must remain within the capabilities of the control system to avoid instability or excessive reliance on burnable poisons.

One strategy to extend the core life is to incorporate breeding capability, particularly in LFRs. However, this approach typically demands a larger core volume to accommodate sufficient fertile material and improve neutron economy, which conflicts with the size and weight constraints of shipboard installation. Increasing the number of control rods (CRs) can help manage reactivity swings, but this brings additional trade-offs: more control rods require additional space and structural complexity, potentially enlarging the core and impacting the overall reactor footprint. Alternatively, increasing the initial fissile content—using fuels such as HALEU (high-assay low-enriched uranium) or MOX (mixed oxide)—can support longer lifetimes. Both options are limited by non-proliferation policies, fuel fabrication challenges, and licensing limitations [6]. Ultimately, designing a marine reactor core involves balancing fuel enrichment, breeding potential, control mechanisms, and physical constraints, all while ensuring compliance with international safety, security, and safeguarding standards.

4. LOAD VARIABILITY AND TRANSIENT RESPONSE IN MARINE REACTOR SYSTEMS

The power demand of a commercial ship varies significantly throughout the different phases of a journey: commercial ships, for example, typically operate at about 70 to 85% propulsion power during transit and at about 10% power during manoeuvring, docking and undocking while, during port calls, power requirement depends on whether the vessel is idle, only hotel load being required, or if engaged in commercial operations requiring, for instance, cargo pumps to run. During these port calls, the reactor should continue supplying auxiliary electrical power, often amounting to only a few percent of nominal output, to support hotel loads, cargo handling systems, and onboard electronics. Fast reactors offer advantages for operation at very low power, not suffering from Xenon poisoning. Shutting down the reactor during these periods is generally undesirable due to the complexity and time required for restart procedures, as well as the need for continuous power availability.

Managing the reactor core—and the broader power system—under low-load conditions presents a complex challenge. Reactor systems must maintain stable operation at reduced power levels, avoiding issues such as thermal stratification, flow instabilities, temperature hot spots, and vibrations. This requires careful design of core geometry, control rod configuration, and coolant flow management, as well as advanced instrumentation and control strategies.

In contrast, certain specialized ships may spend most of their time in port or operating at reduced speed and power, with only brief intervals requiring maximum reactor output—such as during fast maneuvers, rapid deployment, or emergency response. In these scenarios, the reactor must be capable of rapid power ramp-up, reaching full power output within minutes of demand. This imposes stringent

requirements on the control system responsiveness, fuel thermal margins, and mechanical integrity of core components, which must withstand fast transients without compromising safety or performance.

5. FUEL SELECTION

The need to achieve an operational lifetime of around 10–20 years drives the fuel selection process. The ability of both traditional and innovative fuels to handle very high burnup levels is still under investigation in the context of small modular reactors (SMRs) design. However, marine applications exert stress limits on fuel performance, introducing discontinuous power loads and, eventually, mechanical stresses caused by ship movements.

The first and most intuitive requirement is the ability to store high levels of fissile material. Geometry is the main cause of neutron leakage rather than operational lifetime: compactness and high-power density both significantly increase the phenomenon. Therefore, it is necessary to balance these factors by increasing the fission rate. Thanks to their higher atom density, metallic fuels can seem like a possible solution to explore. However, the absence of voids makes them vulnerable to gas swelling and fuel-cladding interactions [7].

Both HALEU and MOX fuels strike a good balance between performance and cost optimisation. However, the former is less accessible due to the large quantity of raw materials required and the manufacturing processes involved, both of which impact the initial investment. Nevertheless, using ^{235}U as a fissile isotope would lead to several technological simplifications. The effective delayed-neutron fraction of a uranium-driven reactor is approximately twice that of an equivalent plutonium-based reactor. Traditional uranium fuel has an effective delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff}) of approximately 650 – 750 pcm, while a range of 350 – 450 pcm was calculated for MOX fuels [8]. This enables CRs of greater value to be planned, thereby increasing the shutdown margin and the reactivity potential that can be handled by the active control system. Another important consequence of this characteristic is that transients are smoother, which provides an additional benefit in accident scenarios.

In terms of production, MOX fuel is competitively priced compared to HALEU. Using irradiated fuel promotes the closure of the fuel cycle and reduces the proliferation issues associated with managing enriched uranium. ^{239}Pu has a higher capture cross-section than ^{235}U resulting in lower fission efficiency [9]. An additional complication relates to the isotopic composition of MOX fuel, which includes the fissile isotopes ^{239}Pu and ^{241}Pu . The latter has a half-life of 14.4 years, comparable to the intended operating lifetime of the design, and undergoes beta decay to ^{241}Am , a strong neutron absorber. As a result, fissile plutonium is progressively lost not only through neutron-induced depletion but also through radioactive decay, leading to the conversion of reactivity worth into parasitic absorption. From a macroscopic perspective, this isotopic evolution translates into a natural loss of reactivity that is proportional to the initial ^{241}Pu content and to the irradiation history. This phenomenon is not observed in HALEU fuel, since the radioactive decay of the fissile isotopes occurs on timescales much longer than the reactor's operational lifetime, making the impact of isotopic transformation on reactivity negligible.

Burnup calculations performed with the deterministic code DRAGON5 provide quantitative support for this interpretation and allow the impact of isotopic degradation to be assessed under different operating conditions [10]. The case study considered a hexagonal fuel assembly, with reflective boundary conditions applied in the radial direction. The results of Figure 1 show that MOX fuel undergoes a more pronounced reduction of the multiplication factor compared to uranium-based fuel over long irradiation times, confirming the dominant role of plutonium depletion and americium buildup in driving fuel degradation. However, the calculations also indicate a clear dependence of the degradation rate on the specific power level. At higher power levels, the decline of the multiplication factor with burnup becomes less steep, reflecting the more efficient consumption of fissile plutonium isotopes and the reduced time available for the beta decay of ^{241}Pu into ^{241}Am . Consequently, the production of americium is mitigated, leading to a slower accumulation of neutron-absorbing isotopes and a reduced rate of reactivity degradation. Therefore, power density emerges as a key design parameter in limiting long-term isotopic degradation and preserving reactivity margins in long-lifetime reactor concepts.

Figure 1. Evolution of the multiplication factor as a function of burnup for HALEU and MOX fuels at different specific power levels.

6. BURNABLE POISONS

In this framework, burnable poisons (BPs) play a key role in the core design, as they allow the reactivity control function to be diversified, thereby reducing the required CRs' worth while increasing its availability. The basic applications of BPs in Gen III marine reactors are well understood. The nuclear ship *Savannah* used fuel rods containing boron impurities, whereas *Otto Hahn* and *Mutsu* had dedicated assemblies for this purpose [5]. In fast reactors, a different approach is taken, favouring the introduction of fertile actinides to exploit the production of fissionable nuclides. This concept was discussed and implemented for SUPER-PHENIX and SNR-2 fuels [11]. Another notable concept is the possibility of loading a sufficient inventory of fertile material to partially compensate fissile depletion through in-situ breeding, thereby limiting the overall reactivity swing over the reactor's lifetime [12]. Of all the options presented, none is clearly preferable in terms of technological expertise or performance potential. Thus, it is necessary to compare traditional materials (e.g. B_4C and GdO_2) with more promising technologies (e.g. AmO_2 and NpO_2), proposing a range of solutions to be investigated during the design phase [13].

B_4C is one of the most popular options for BP owing to its extensive use in conventional reactors, where it serves as both a BP and a CR material. It has one of the highest microscopic absorption cross sections of all isotopes, both in the thermal and fast spectrum. However, preliminary calculations by newcleo have shown that ^{10}B is not fully consumed during burnup, even when it is initially inserted in smaller quantities. This results in a substantial residual reactivity penalty at the end of life. Lastly, it should be noted that ^{10}B generates tritium (3H) and helium under irradiation which diffuse and generate stress inside the cladding. This issue is more severe than for land-based applications, where control rods and fuel elements are replaced periodically.

Minor actinides (MA) are a promising candidate for BP in fast reactors applications, as the possibility to burn them addresses the issue of long-term nuclear waste management while improving fuel performance. As previously mentioned, ^{241}Am , ^{243}Am and ^{237}Np are strong neutron absorbers which transmute into Pu isotopes through capture and decay. Thus, they initially provide a negative contribution to the chain reaction, but this reverses under irradiation [14]. Due to their high cost, MA are only a suitable solution if most of the initial concentration is consumed. For special-purpose ships, where the number of equivalent effective full-power days is small compared to the operating lifetime, traditional, lower-cost materials are more convenient. Technological issues related to the use of MA furthermore derive from difficulties in extracting them from nuclear spent fuel. Finally, in the design process, it is necessary to consider the emission of alpha particles from decay and the production of gaseous fission products from MA.

Hafnium-based materials received some attention for marine applications, especially in very long-life reactors [5]. CRs made from Hf alloys have been used in the *Nautilus'* reactor thanks to their ability to

maintain absorber behaviour even under irradiation: interactions with neutrons mostly transform Hf isotopes into other isotopes of the same element without generating gaseous daughters. Therefore, even if the reactivity penalty introduced is lower than that of traditional materials, its effect lasts longer. Due to these properties, Hf can be defined as a non-burnable poison since it cannot be consumed. Nevertheless, it remains a promising option for control elements and shielding components.

Several Monte Carlo particle transport simulations were carried out in support of the presented arguments. OpenMC v0.15.0 was used for this analysis as it already has a depletion module implemented. A first-order predictor algorithm was chosen to solve the Bateman equation [15]. The case study involved a hexagonal fuel assembly loaded with MOX fuel. Reflecting boundary conditions were applied radially with vacuum boundary conditions at the top and bottom surfaces. Different neutron poisons were introduced to evaluate their impact. The oxide materials (AmO_2 , NpO_2 and HfO_2) were assumed to be uniformly distributed within the fuel matrix, whereas boron carbide (B_4C) was confined to specific pins. The quantity of poison loaded initially was such that the different burnable poisons gave nearly the same initial reactivity penalty, allowing to focus the discussion on the slope of the reactivity curves. Figure 2 shows the simulation results for a constant power of 0.4 MW for the entire assembly. The effective multiplication factor of each system is presented as a function of operating time. It is necessary to specify that the initial reactivity penalty is caused by two competing factors: the introduction of a neutron absorber and the reduction in fuel inventory due to the substitution by BP. Overall, the density of boron carbide is more than three times lower than that of oxide materials, whose values are roughly equivalent to those of the fuel. Therefore, if the same mass of fuel is substituted, B_4C will exhibit a larger reactivity penalty. The natural isotopic composition is used for boron carbide and hafnium oxide. Meanwhile, Np is composed entirely of ^{237}Np and Am from 65% of ^{241}Am and 35% of ^{243}Am . These compositions are extracted from estimations of spent fuel irradiated inside a pressurised water reactor.

The most important data to observe in Fig. 2 is the reactivity gap recovered during the depletion process: the flatter the curve, the better the poison. Looking at the slope of the curves, it is possible to create a qualitative ranking of the analysed solutions: AmO_2 performs best with the lowest reactivity swing, followed by NpO_2 , B_4C and finally HfO_2 for which the reactivity gap even increases during depletion. The ranking of the different burnable poisons can be understood from analysing the cross sections of the different poisons and the isotopes they transmute into. Hf is ineffective because its isotopes transmute into absorber nuclides, resulting in a negative contribution to poison consumption. Boron is more efficient because its capture cross section is significantly higher than that of its daughters. However, the most efficient burnable poisons are the minor actinides because they transmute from absorbers into fissile isotopes.

Figure 2. Effect on the effective multiplication factor for different burnable poisons.

7. REACTIVITY CONTROL AND SHUTDOWN SYSTEMS IN MARINE REACTOR ENVIRONMENTS

As discussed in the previous section, the reactivity control function in marine reactors should be diversified, combining distributed burnable poisons with dedicated mechanical systems. In this context, reactivity control and shutdown systems shall be designed to operate reliably under conditions that are rarely encountered in land-based installations. Unlike stationary terrestrial reactors, shipboard reactors are subject to continuous motion, including pitching, rolling, and vibration caused by waves, propulsion systems, and maneuvering. These dynamic conditions shall not induce unintended reactivity changes or compromise the effectiveness of control mechanisms. Components must therefore be resistant to mechanical shock, misalignment, and wear, and must maintain precise positioning even under variable acceleration and orientation. Hydraulic or electromagnetic control rod systems are often preferred for their robustness and responsiveness in such environment.

Beyond routine motions, marine reactors shall also be engineered to withstand extreme and incidental conditions, including capsizing, flooding, and sinking, which are design base conditions for this type of applications. In such scenarios, the reactor shall enter a safe shutdown state automatically, halting the nuclear chain reaction and maintaining subcriticality without relying on external power or operator intervention. This requires the integration of passive safety systems, negative reactivity feedback mechanisms, and fail-safe actuation designs.

Furthermore, the reactor shall remain in a cold shutdown condition even if submerged or tilted, with decay heat removal systems capable of functioning in altered orientations or compromised environments. The core could be structurally reinforced to prevent distortion or displacement of fuel assemblies under hydrostatic pressure or mechanical shock. Shutdown rods must be locked in a way that guarantees their insertion and holdown regardless of orientation—whether upright, tilted, or inverted. This may involve mechanical latching systems, spring-loaded drives, or magnetically coupled actuators designed to function independently of gravity and in case of flooding.

8. SAFEGUARDS AND SECURITY

The deployment of nuclear-powered ships requires a comprehensive framework encompassing safety, security, and safeguards to protect the crew, the public, the marine environment, and the cargo. These considerations are inherently delicate and must be integrated from the earliest design stages.

Nuclear safety is ensured through a defence-in-depth approach that combines robust reactor design, multiple physical barriers, redundant safety systems, and continuous monitoring. These features shall be engineered to prevent incidents and to guarantee safe shutdown under all credible conditions. Lead-cooled reactors incorporate passive safety systems and, in marine applications, benefit from the sea itself as an effective virtually infinite heat sink. This enables the removal of decay heat without reaching temperatures that could damage the structural elements of the reactor core.

Security is maintained through a layered physical protection system that restricts access to sensitive areas, employs surveillance and intrusion-detection technologies, and relies on trained onboard security personnel. Threat-response capabilities shall align with and enhance maritime security protocols (e.g. the International Ship and Port Security Code, ISPS) to mitigate risks ranging from unauthorized access to potential hostile actions.

Safeguards and non-proliferation measures ensure the responsible management of nuclear materials, consistent with the practices in all existing nuclear installations. This includes comprehensive fuel accounting, secure handling and transport procedures, and compliance with national and international oversight bodies. A key design principle is to limit fissile material strictly to the core and fuel elements and to prevent unauthorized access. Multiple layers of protective measures—such as reactor vessel designs that cannot be opened without specialized tools and the use of molten lead coolant, which inherently obstructs access—make the extraction of fissile materials virtually impossible during malevolent attacks.

Finally, fuel selection plays an important role. Both MOX and HALEU fuels, when enriched within the isotopic ranges permitted for civilian applications, present limited proliferation concerns—particularly

after irradiation in the reactor, when the resulting radiation fields make handling impossible without specialized facilities available only in dedicated shipyards.

9. INSTALLATION AND LIFETIME CONSIDERATIONS FOR LEAD-COOLED REACTOR CORE

The marine regulatory framework requires that propulsion and steering of a nuclear ship vessel shall be guaranteed also in the event of a single point failure affecting either the reactor, the power conversion system, or the propulsion train. This implies a certain level of redundancy in respect to power generation and propulsion train to ensure the availability of the minimum propulsive power needed to ensure safe manoeuvring in rough seas.

In conventional ships, the main engine room is typically located aft, directly below the superstructure, preventing direct access to the main diesel engine from above. For nuclear vessels, this arrangement should be reconsidered, possibly by positioning the reactor compartment and turbine hall forward of the superstructure, while reserving the space beneath it for auxiliary systems and tankage. A substantial rearrangement of the engine room layout is therefore required. In any case, once the reactor becomes operational, maintenance interventions and direct access to the core must be minimized.

The relevant flag administration will define the minimum safe manning requirements for nuclear-powered ships, including both the number of personnel onboard and their qualification and training standards. For Advanced Marine Reactors, the “nuclear crew” is expected to perform primarily supervisory and watchkeeping functions, as load-following operations will be fully automated. This approach enables limiting the number of onboard personnel, provided that specific training on the nuclear system is ensured. Furthermore, strong integration with a 24/7 Onshore Fleet Control Room staffed by highly trained nuclear operators can further limit the number of nuclear operators required onboard.

The installation of a lead-cooled reactor core represents one of the most critical phases in the deployment of a marine nuclear power system, primarily due to the need to guarantee subcriticality throughout the process. The established practice involves the use of a dummy core, identical in geometry to the final configuration but containing no active fuel pins. This allows the reactor vessel to be safely filled with liquid lead coolant before gradually replacing the dummy elements with actual fuel assemblies and control components.

While already complex in land-based installations, where specialized equipment and controlled environments are available, this procedure becomes significantly more challenging in a shipyard setting. Restricted accessibility and the ship’s structural layout impose additional constraints on handling, positioning, and alignment of heavy and highly sensitive reactor components. Consequently, the reactor core design directly influences the configuration and capabilities of the shipyard, which must be equipped with dedicated lifting and positioning systems capable of millimeter-level precision. Temperature control systems may also be required to maintain coolant properties – for instance, keeping lead in a liquid state during pre-commissioning and commissioning – further increasing complexity compared to conventional shipbuilding. “Nuclear Shipyards” shall therefore be considered as designed and outfitted to carry out installation, commissioning, and maintenance of nuclear powered ships, while “Nuclear Scrapyards” shall be considered for long-term decommissioning, including facilities for the safe removal, transport, and storage of irradiated components. For these reasons, the installation methodology must be defined at the earliest stages of the core and reactor design process, ensuring that assembly, operation, maintenance and final dismantling can be carried out safely and efficiently.

10. CONCLUSIONS

Nuclear powered ships present challenges far beyond those posed by land-based reactors, requiring the integration of core physics, fuel-cycle strategy, reactivity control, ship installation logistics, and shipyard / scarpyard infrastructure. Achieving reliable, low-maintenance systems depends on addressing these factors from the outset. Marine reactors shall support very long lifetimes, manage reactivity with burnable poisons and advanced fuels such as HALEU or MOX, and balance compactness, shielding, and durability. They must also be able to operate safely under low-load conditions while retaining the ability for rapid load-following, placing high demands on control

systems and thermal-hydraulic stability.

Because shipboard reactors face unique operational and environmental risks, shutdown systems and core configuration must ensure subcriticality, coolable geometry, and passive heat removal under all circumstances, including extreme events. Core design and installation directly shape shipyard requirements, from heavy-lifting capabilities to long-term decommissioning facilities. The future of nuclear powered ships lies in integrated design strategies that anticipate operational variability, installation constraints, and long-term sustainability—combining advanced fuel cycles, innovative reactivity management, and purpose-built shipyard infrastructure to deliver safe, reliable, and adaptable power systems supporting maritime decarbonization.

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